

The Importance of Fertility Awareness

Fertility awareness is overlooked across Europe, with very few countries providing fundamental knowledge in schools to youngsters, including Denmark and the UK. One of the many factors explaining this is governments' pressure to cater to the opposite problem: contraception. Unfortunately, what is ignored is that contraception and fertility are part of the same issue, two sides of the same coin. Teaching the young about fertility and taking care of factors influencing their reproductive health helps them make the right choices.

"We would like to arm the young with the knowledge to make the right choices at the right time";- Says Anita Fincham on behalf of Fertility Europe. "Being better informed about fertility will empower the population in order to make their decisions not just healthier for themselves, but also their future children", says Dr Güell. Fertility must not be taken for granted, as macroscopic data reveals: 1 out of 10 couples has infertility at the moment, and birth rates have significantly decreased in the western world. In fact, in 2019, the total fertility rate in the EU was 1.53 live births per woman, according to EUROSTAT.

Family planning dynamics have changed over time, as more opportunities for self-fulfilment in one's life are available, which has led to a different timeline for any individual to decide to have children. In addition, the conception of the family itself has changed. All these are positive changes that must be supported, but the freedom of any given individual to have children of their own must be guaranteed.

Knowledge is power.